

Protocol for a modified meta-narrative review of conceptualisations and meanings of ‘open-source communities’ within and across research traditions

Registration:

Final protocol uploaded to Zenodo: doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13740342

Authors:

Sol Martinez Demarco, Project INKleSS, Faculty of Business Studies, Harz University of Applied Sciences

smartinezdemarco@hs-harz.de

Dr. Alena Bleicher, Faculty of Business Studies, Harz University of Applied Sciences

ableicher@hs-harz.de

Background

A particularly challenging aspect of software development are phenomena of ignorance, such as tacit knowledge, forgetting, or unawareness, that come with implementing, maintaining, updating, and upgrading increasingly complex pieces of software. So far, however, ignorance, its causes, and its relevance in free, libre, and open-source (F/LOSS) communities have not been studied. We argue that it is important to research phenomena of ignorance to understand their consequences, which in many cases will be embedded in our everyday digital lives. For example, a forgotten and no longer maintained version of the open-source operative system Android still running on a mobile phone creates security risks such as identity theft.

We assume that open-source communities are social structures where phenomena of organisational ignorance such as strategic ignorance, uncomfortable knowledge, and categorical blindness are relevant. Research on organisations has shown that organisational structures, design, and culture impact related phenomena of ignorance (Jalonen, 2023). In order to study phenomena of ignorance, it is therefore important to be aware of the structures of open-source communities.

Research on these communities, from Raymond (1999) ‘s *The Cathedral and the Bazaar* to recent ethnographic work on the *Ruby* programming language community (Heurich 2024) has highlighted the different ways in which F/LOSS communities can be organised. Open-source projects are characterised for example by the ideas of free access and reuse of source code, which require certain knowledge, skills and abilities of participating individuals, as well as by the length of time the projects have existed, the dynamic of their development and activities and material artefacts. These, in turn, influence their structure and governance. However, to the best of our knowledge, there has been no systematic and comprehensive review of the characteristics and classifications of these communities that have been suggested in diverse research contexts (e.g. Tamburri et al. 2013, Tamburri et al. 2019, Schrape 2019). An overview on existing conceptualisations is however needed, to direct social scientific research on

phenomena such as ignorance. Therefore, a literature review in the form of a modified meta-narrative review is proposed to be carried out. In this protocol we introduce the objectives, methodology and expected outcomes of this meta-narrative review.

Research objectives

The overall aim of this meta-narrative review is the development of a taxonomy that takes into account existing typologies of F/LOSS communities in order to study phenomena of ignorance in these communities from a social scientific perspective. In other words, it is the first step into the analysis of how programming communities can be approached from the field of ignorance studies. This implies a systematic literature analysis of research published on open-source software development communities in a multitude of disciplines, the identification of different research traditions within said disciplines and their understanding of free, libre and open-source communities including their definitions and characterisations. The analysis of conceptualisations from different research traditions contributes to their articulation and the establishment of a framework for understanding different beliefs and ideas, which, in turn, inform the narratives corresponding to those traditions, in line with the meta-narrative approach adopted for this review. As a final outcome, the narratives will support the development of a meta-narrative and its associated taxonomy.

The research questions that this review seek to answer are the following: (1) What are the main research traditions that have considered the broad topic area of FLOSS communities, and how do they conceptualise open-source communities? (2) What are the main concepts and related characteristics of communities highlighted within these research traditions? (3) What methods have they used? (in order to identify implicit understandings about what constitute a community) (4) In how far it is possible to combine the conceptualisations from these different traditions? What insights can be drawn by comparing them?

In sum, the results of the review are a number of narratives, a meta-narrative, and the associated taxonomy, as already explained. These, in turn, will be combined with findings from studies on organizational ignorance to support the project to of which this review forms part. By connecting these strands of research with the conceptual considerations on communities therein, the taxonomy functions as sensitising tool for the future research tasks and objectives of the main project (a doctoral dissertation), of which this review is one element.

Methods and design

A meta-narrative review is a type of review “designed for topics that have been differently (sic) conceptualized and studied by different groups of researchers (Wong et al., 2013, p. 2).” As a specific type of literature review, the pioneering work conducted by Greenhalgh and colleagues (2005) explains their proposal for carrying out a meta-narrative as the outcome of three challenges that emerged when addressing topic areas that have been studied by incompatible research traditions.

- Fuzzy and contested definitions that emerge from qualitative and quantitative research, which are not amenable to comparison, and make inclusion criteria for primary studies very difficult.
- Lack of knowledge about where to look for good research studies and how to define 'quality studies'.
- Too narrow a focus would lead to missing out studies from other research traditions, which could provide valuable knowledge or ideas (Greenhalgh et al., 2005, p. 418).

Furthermore, a meta-narrative review usually follows a two-stage approach. Firstly, "the review seeks to identify and understand as many as possible of the potentially important different research traditions which have a bearing on the topic, and [secondly, it] synthe[sises] them by means of an over-arching narrative. The goal of meta-narrative review is sensemaking of a complex topic area (Wong et al., 2013, p. 6)." To elaborate these narratives researchers summarise data from quantitative and qualitative research works, identify and analyse the relationships between different themes and concepts, and consider contextual factors that affect the topic over time. The documentation of the evolution or progression of the research agenda in the various research traditions identified depict how theories and methodologies have changed (Mengistu and Manolova, 2019). According to Jamal et al. (2015, p. 329), "the historical dimension and in particular the breadth of chronological scope, allow[s] to consider what external factors in social, economic or political life might influence the emerging narratives."

More specifically, Greenhalgh et al. (2005), who developed the review and deployed it for the first time, divide the work in six phases, which overlap and inform each other.

1. Planning phase:

Includes assembling a multidisciplinary team with background in the relevant research traditions, propose an initial broad research question, and set up a series of regular review meetings (which can include input from outside peers who will be part of the audience of the review). Identify the audience(s).

2. Search phase:

Based on intuition guiding the work, the search takes an informal shape, including networking and browsing to map the diversity of perspectives and approaches. Also, it covers the identification of seminal/foundational conceptual papers in each research tradition by tracking references of references, and their evaluation by their quality, comprehensiveness and contribution to the field.

3. Mapping phase:

The objective is to identify for each research tradition:

- Key elements of the research paradigm: conceptual, theoretical, methodological and instrumental.
- Key actors and events as well as the main findings and their process of 'discovery'.

- Prevailing language and imagery used for ‘telling the story’.

4. Appraisal phase:

Using critical appraisal techniques it includes:

- The evaluation of each primary study for its validity and relevance for the research question.
- The extraction, collection and grouping into key results.

5. Synthesis phase:

- Identification of key dimensions.
- For each dimension provision of a narrative account of the contribution made by each research tradition.
- Presentation of each conflicting finding as contestations between different paradigms and their data.

6. Recommendation phase:

- Summary of the main stories and relevant evidence.
- Elaboration and discussion of recommendations for practice and further research.

In terms of guiding research questions, Table 1 presents two possible set of questions.

Table 1. Possible guiding questions for meta-narrative reviews

Guiding questions proposed by Greenhalgh et al. (2005, pp. 420-421)	Guiding questions proposed by Wong et al. (2013, p. 5)
(a) What are the parameters of [each] tradition, i.e. its scope, its historical roots, its key concepts and assumptions, and its theoretical basis?	(1) Which research (or epistemic) traditions have considered this broad topic area?
(b) What research questions [addressing their priority as well] have scientists in this tradition asked about [the topic]? What methods and instruments have they used to answer those questions, and by what criteria has methodological quality of primary studies generally been judged?	(2) How has each tradition conceptualized the topic (for example, including assumptions about the nature of reality, preferred study designs and ways of knowing)?
(c) What are the main empirical findings of relevance from the quality literature in this research tradition?	(3) What theoretical approaches and methods did they use?
(d) How has the tradition unfolded over time (i.e. in what way have the findings of earlier studies led to refinements in theory and/or	(4) What are the main empirical findings?;

influenced the design and direction of later empirical work)?	
(e) What are the strengths and limitations of this tradition, and in the light of these, what is its likely overall contribution to the body of knowledge on this topic area?	(5) What insights can be drawn by combining and comparing findings from different traditions?.

As these two sets of questions indicate, there are a variety of research avenues to pursue, but resources and time are finite, therefore the expectation is to progressively ‘contain’ the review, by calibrating the breadth (how wide the area?) and the depth (how much detail?). The justification and processes of negotiation and evolution of research questions, objectives, and/or breadth and depth are worth reporting.

Finally, it is important to stress that meta-narrative reviews are inherently iterative and shapeshifting, thus Greenhalgh et al. (2005) suggest to conduct any meta-narrative review observing the following five key principles:

- Pragmatism: choices are subjective and negotiable; moving from a first exploratory and emergent search, the process is guided by the needs and perspective of the audience (Greenhalgh et al., 2005, p. 427).
- Pluralism: “the challenge is to expose the tensions, map the diversity and communicate the complexity of how the various different traditions contribute to an understanding of the problem as a whole (ibid.)”
- Historicity: a narrative needs of a sequence of events in time to create a plot, in this case, of key scientific discoveries and insights that lead to expanding a body of knowledge.
- Contestation: due to the heterogeneity of research questions, methods, results and conclusions, the way forward is to find higher-level interpretations or explanations for the differences and recommendations from different traditions.
- Peer-review: to continually seek to test against external (formal and informal) peers the emerging findings is of utmost importance for research that is highly complex and whose methods are emergent.

The paper that will report the outcomes of the review based on this protocol will follow the RAMESES (Realist And MEta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards) publication standards (Wong et al., 2013) and its associated quality criteria (Greenhalgh and Wong, 2013; Greenhalgh et al., 2005). In this sense, the application of the pragmatism principle imposes for this project mayor changes in the traditional meta-narrative approach. Generally, the planning phase covers the assembly of a review team, usually composed of more than two members and with diverse expertise and knowledge background. In our case, (as a first element of a doctoral dissertation), the team consists of only two authors, the doctoral candidate and their first supervisor. In addition, review meetings incorporate input from

external peers, who are part of the research project that frames the doctoral research, and the identified audiences are part of different scientific disciplines, and will be expected to provide feedback throughout the research process as preliminary results of this review are presented in various academic venues. More importantly, this meta-narrative review will only partially follow the five main guiding questions (Table 1) of this type of literature review. The main differences lie on focusing only on conceptualisation of a term (definitions and characteristics), without identification of quality criteria and empirical results, and in line with Jamal et al. (2015) avoiding the categorisation of authors' theoretical positionality. This protocol is registered with Zenodo.

1. Planning phase

As previously explain, the team consists of the two authors of this protocol, the doctoral candidate and their first supervisor. They both have developed the research questions and SMD has drafted the protocol, while AB has assisted in refining and finalising it. In addition, review meetings incorporate input from external peers, who are part of the research project that frames the doctoral research, and deliver additional assistance if required. Also, the identified audiences are part of different scientific disciplines, and will be expected to provide feedback throughout the research process when preliminary results of this review are presented in various academic venues.

At this stage, the four research questions previously introduced, were developed: (1) What are the main research traditions that have considered the broad topic area of FLOSS communities, and how do they conceptualise open-source communities? (2) What are the main concepts and related characteristics of communities highlighted within these research traditions? (3) What methods have they used? (in order to identify implicit understandings about what constitute a community) (4) In how far it is possible to combine the conceptualisations from these different traditions? What insights can be drawn by comparing them?

2. Searching phase

The objective of this phase is the collection of a comprehensive list of literature on the topic area capturing the diversity of research traditions and conceptualisations. This review, as secondary research, takes this literature as the primary data source, which will be analysed to elaborate each research traditions' narrative and, in turn, they will contribute to the production of the meta-narrative. To achieve a balance between comprehensiveness and focus, the search will be guided, as in the case of Kim et al. (2021) by the concept of saturation. This "is achieved when no new insights are generated by collecting additional data (Kim et al., 2021, p. 3)." Once the review team observes, during the appraisal and/or synthesis phase(s), conceptual repetition of findings in the data, saturation will have been attained (ibid.).

Our search strategy covers three main avenues: (a) a search in electronic databases using keywords, (b) a double-sided snowballing (forward- and backward looking) references search,

and (c) a hand search. The keywords will be applied to searches to be conducted in platforms hosting multidisciplinary scientific databases (Scopus, Web of Science, and ProQuest) and computing- and engineering-specific libraries (ACM Digital Library and IEEE Explore). The search string uses Boolean operators “AND” and “OR” and will be formatted for each database. The keywords included are shown in the following table:

Research Subject	Trait
open-source community	taxonomy
coding community	typology
programming community	classification
software development community	conceptualis(z)ation
social coding community	framework
organis(z)ation	definition
	characteristics
	aspects

A pilot test was conducted to assess the best search strategy. Based on the utility of a more complex search, modifications were made to the first proposal indicated in a previous version of this protocol.

The literature to collect includes qualitative, quantitative and/or mixed-methods research works as well as non-empirical studies based on the following criteria: (a) they are written in English, (b) published between 1984 (a few months after Richard Stallman announced the GNU Project¹) and 2024 (to be up-to-date), as (c) journal articles, reviews, book chapters, books, articles in conference proceedings, or thesis. They must explicitly address the topic of F/LOSS communities to be eligible for inclusion.

All the publications identified will be exported (using RIS files) to Eppi Reviewer 6², a software tool for systematic reviews, to be screened for inclusion in the review. Furthermore, these records will be imported and managed using Citavi, a reference manager software, and several groups will be created to track the records at each step. Duplicated records and those without abstract or incomplete information will be deleted before the initial screening phase. SMD will conduct the screening in two rounds: title and abstract, and full-text. At the second screening round, both reviewers will assess a sample of the records to establish screening consistency, and after reaching at least 80 per cent of agreement, they will independently screen the remaining literature, as suggested by Mengistu and Manolova (2019). In case of disagreement the reviewers will discuss and reach an agreement. The number of records and the reasons for inclusion/exclusion during each round will be clarified in the final review article and illustrated by means of a PRISMA flow diagram (Page et al., 2021).

¹ <https://groups.google.com/g/net.unix-wizards/c/8twfRPM79u0/m/1xlgizrWrU0J>

² <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/eppireviewer-web/home>

3. Mapping phase

Seminal papers will be identified first because as central contributions to each research tradition and the research topic, they provide early definitions of concepts and theories, and are continuously cited in later works. Mapping them, will allow to identify different paradigms and connections among all the included records. These papers will be assessed according to the following criteria, adopted from Jamal et al. (2015, p. 320) and modified accordingly:

- Of which research tradition is the paper part of?
- Does the paper make an original contribution into the meaning or conceptualisation of coding community?
- Has the paper subsequently been cited as a seminal contribution by researchers in that tradition?

Both reviewers will analyse a subset of these articles independently and meet later to compare assessments. As explained before, once a broad agreement has been achieved the rest of the studies will be divided between the reviewers. Using Eppi Reviewer 6, the information extracted from these landmark works will complement the development of the data extraction form to be developed, covering not only the predefined terms, but also the ones determined by the analysis of the seminal works.

4. Appraisal phase

The code system developed through the analysis of the seminal publications and the predefined terms during the mapping phase will be incorporated to MaxQDA, a qualitative research software, to be used to code the papers to be reviewed, ensuring transparency in the collaborative process. At the end of the process, a table will summarise the main findings of each work. During this phase the modified criteria based on Jamal et al. (2015) will also be used to evaluate each article.

All data will be stored in the approved research data storage system provided by the authors' institution and handled in accordance with data management practices and a guideline to be developed based on usual practices in the social sciences.

5. Synthesis phase

During this phase, the reviewers will synthesise the data in two steps: (1) they elaborate the conceptual frameworks, and narratives of each research tradition, and (2) they work on a meta-narrative, a taxonomy and the associated meta-conceptual framework. Informed by conceptual framework analysis (Ravitch & Mittenfelner Carl, 2019; Jabareen, 2009) this review looks to elaborate a meta-conceptual framework that is based on the multidisciplinary knowledge present in the literature collected to act as "the compass, the landmarks, the navigation system (Ravitch & Mittenfelner Carl, 2019, p. 35)" for the doctoral dissertation.

After the data analysis is completed, the reviewers will meet to discuss the emerging concepts and their descriptions and overarching narratives, as well as how they unfold over time (Mengitsu & Manolova, 2019). This phase will focus on the concepts identified, and an analysis of their strengths and weaknesses with regard to the intended research, their overlaps and contradictions as well as the gaps and limitations of these conceptualisations. Developing, discussing and agreeing on the meta-narrative, which highlights conflicts and tensions within the literature analysed, will be the milestone of this review, as it will provide the elements for the next step of the process, studying phenomena of ignorance in these communities.

6. Recommendation phase

The final phase of this type of systematic review usually includes drafting a final report and elaborating recommendations for further research into the topic. However, as an element of a doctoral research, explicit recommendations will not be made, but the doctoral candidate will strive for the identification of specific questions regarding how to study organisational ignorance based on the meta-narrative and associated taxonomy. Furthermore, the doctoral candidate will aim for publications in peer-reviewed journals to present the various components of this review, including protocol, meta-narrative review findings, and follow-up work at the intersection of open-source communities and ignorance studies.

References

- Greenhalgh, T., Robert, G., Macfarlane, F., Bate, P., Kyriakidou, O., & Peacock, R. (2005). Storylines of research in diffusion of innovation: A meta-narrative approach to systematic review. *Social Science & Medicine*, 61(2), 417–430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2004.12.001>
- Greenhalgh, T., & Wong, G. (2013). *Training materials for meta-narrative reviews*. http://www.ramesesproject.org/media/Meta_narrative_reviews_training_materials.pdf
- Heurich, G. O. (2024). *Coderspeak: The language of computer programmers*. UCL Press.
- Jabareen, Y. (2009). Building a Conceptual Framework: Philosophy, Definitions, and Procedure. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 8(4), 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690900800406>
- Jalonen, H. (2023). Ignorance in organisations – a systematic literature review. *Management Review Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-023-00321-z>
- Jamal, F., Bertotti, M., Lorenc, T., & Harden, A. (2015). Reviewing conceptualisations of community: Reflections on a meta-narrative approach. *Qualitative Research*, 15(3), 314–333. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794113509262>
- Kim, J., Harris-Roxas, B., de Leeuw, E., Lilley, D., Crimeen, A., & Sainsbury, P. (2021). Protocol for a meta-narrative review on research paradigms addressing the urban built environment and human health. *Systematic Reviews*, 10(1), 311. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01848-6>
- Mengistu, B. S., & Manolova, G. (2019). Acculturation and mental health among adult forced migrants: A meta-narrative systematic review protocol. *Systematic Reviews*, 8(1), 184. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1103-8>
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... McKenzie, J. E. (2021). PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n160. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>
- Ravitch, S. M., & Mittenfelner Carl, N. (2019). Conceptual Frameworks in Research. In *Qualitative Research: Bridging the Conceptual, Theoretical, and Methodological* (Second Edition, pp. 32–61). SAGE Publications.
- Raymond, E. S. (1999). *The Cathedral and the Bazaar: Musings on Linux and Open Source by an Accidental Revolutionary*. O'Reilly.
- Schrape, J.-F. (2019). Open-source projects as incubators of innovation: From niche phenomenon to integral part of the industry. *Convergence*, 25(3), 409–427. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856517735795>
- Tamburri, D. A., Lago, P., van Vliet, H. (2013). Organizational social structures for software engineering. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 46(1), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2522968.2522971>

Tamburri, D.A., Palomba, F., Serebrenik, A., Zaidman, A. (2019). Discovering community patterns in open-source: a systematic approach and its evaluation. *Empir Software Eng* 24, 1369–1417. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-018-9659-9>

Wong, G., Greenhalgh, T., Westhorp, G., Buckingham, J., & Pawson, R. (2013). RAMESES publication standards: Meta-narrative reviews. *BMC Medicine*, 11(20), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-11-20>